

Linked Data Cubes: Research results so far

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Abstract. During the last years a growing body of literature studied Linked Data Cubes. The objective of this paper is to accumulate this body of knowledge and provide a preliminary analysis of the research results in the area so far. Towards this end, we systematically reviewed the scientific literature to identify relevant studies. These studies were analysed and synthesised in the form of a proposed conceptual framework, which was thereafter applied to further analyse this literature, hence gaining new insights into the field. The framework comprises three dimensions, namely category of contribution, step of data analysis, and application area. The application of the framework resulted in interesting findings. For example, the majority of the contributions that focus on publishing linked data cubes are cases while the majority of the exploitation contributions are software tools. Moreover, integration of data cubes remains largely unexamined in the literature. This paper, however, does not present the final results of the analysis of the literature as this is still an ongoing activity.

Keywords: Data cubes; linked data; statistics; data analytics; review.

1 Introduction

Statistical data is often organised in a multidimensional manner where a measured fact is described based on a number of dimensions, e.g. unemployment rate could be described based on geographic area, time and gender. In this case, statistical data is compared to a data cube, where each cell contains a measure or a set of measures, and thus we onwards refer to statistical multidimensional data as data cubes or just cubes [2].

Linked data has been introduced as a promising technological paradigm that facilitates data integration on the Web [1]. In the case of cubes, linked data has the potential to transform the Web to a platform for performing statistical analysis on top of combined data enabling this way the realisation of innovative data analytics scenarios [3]. As a result, during the last years, a growing number of research contributions in the area of “linked data cubes” have been published in journals and proceedings of conferences and workshops.

The aim of this paper is to consolidate this body of knowledge and provide a preliminary understanding of the research results in the area so far. Towards this end, we systematically reviewed the scientific literature to identify relevant studies. These studies were analysed and synthesised in the form of a proposed conceptual framework, which was thereafter applied to further analyse this literature, hence gaining new insights into the field.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the approach that we followed to achieve the objectives of the paper. Section 3 presents the conceptual framework that structures the area of linked data cubes. Section 4 presents the results of the analysis of the literature based on the conceptual framework. Finally, section 5 draws conclusions.

2 Approach

A systematic literature review [4] was conducted to achieve the objectives of this paper. At first, a systematic search was used to acquire a large number of relevant scientific papers. The authors initially systematically searched Google scholar using “linked data” AND “data cube” as key words. The search resulted in the collection of an initial pool of articles. These articles were used as a starting point to a) go backward by reviewing their citations and b) go forward by using the functionality provided by Google scholar that allows to find articles citing the previously identified articles. The articles identified from the previous process were studied and filtered resulting in a final set of 136 articles. These articles have been published in scientific journals, or presented in scientific conferences and workshops and can be found in the final section of this paper (Literature Review References).

Moreover, a concept-centric analysis was used to synthesize the acquired knowledge. Specifically, the main characteristics of the area were extracted and a conceptual framework for linked data cubes was created in order to structure the area. Finally, the framework was used to classify and further analyse the literature and to extract insights into the area of linked data cubes.

3 Framework

The proposed framework (Fig. 1) comprises three dimensions:

- The type of contributions in the literature. This includes software, architecture, formal theory, vocabulary, and use case. Some of these categories are further divided into sub-categories. For example, the vocabulary type can be related either to a definition of a vocabulary or the application of a vocabulary.
- The linked data cube analysis steps. These include data cube publishing, exploiting, combining, quality assurance, and access control. Two of the steps are further divided. The exploiting step can refer to (a) browsing, (b) OLAP analysis, (c) visualisation, and (d) statistical analysis. Moreover, quality assurance can refer to either instance-level quality or schema-level quality.

- Application areas such as health, finance, and environment.

Fig. 1. The linked data cube framework

The dimensions define a three-dimensional space which structures the area and enables the categorisation and further analysis of the literature. For example, a contribution in the literature may refer to a vocabulary that enables access control in linked data cubes in health [65].

4 Results

We now employ the framework in order to gain insight into the research on linked data cubes. We initially categorise the articles based on the three dimensions.

Using only the “Analysis Step” dimension we can categorise the literature into the five steps. The vast majority of the contributions are related to publishing (42%) and exploitation (37%). The rest of the contributions are related to combining (13%), “Quality” (5%), and “Access” (3%). If we drill-down in the “Exploit” step, then we can see that 38% of the contributions refer to visualisation, 29% to OLAP analysis, 26% to statistical analysis, and 7% to browsing.

Using only the “Category” dimension of the framework we can categorise the literature based on the different types of contributions. The vast majority of the contributions describe use cases (38%) and present software tools (38%). Other types of contributions include vocabularies (15%), formal theory (7%), and architectures (2%).

Interestingly, taking into account only the “Application Area” dimension, we can see that 40% of the contributions are domain-specific. These contributions span a wide range of domains including health, policy-making, government, environment, economics, biology, and tourism. The most notable domain is health that characterises 25% of all domain-specific contributions.

By synthesizing the results, we can further analyse the literature and make some interesting observations regarding the research contributions so far. First, it is very important to combine the “Category” and “Analysis Step” dimensions. By doing so we can get two different views of the literature, (a) the types of contributions in relation to the analysis step and (b) the analysis steps in relation to the types of contributions. The vast majority (64%) of the use cases in the literature are about publishing and only 20% and 13% respectively describe cases of exploiting and combining. Software contributions mainly focus on requirements related to exploitation (56%). Out of these exploitation software contributions 55% enables creating visualisations, 24% enables performing statistical analysis, 13% enables browsing, and 8% enables performing OLAP operations on top of linked data cubes. The rest of the software contributions facilitate publishing (25%), support combining (19%), ensure cubes’ quality (6%), and enable controlling access (3%) to linked data cubes. Interestingly, half of the contributions that introduce vocabularies support the publishing of linked data cubes (such as the RDF data cube vocabulary). The rest of the vocabulary related contributions focus on (a) facilitating the exploitation (36%) of linked data cubes, (b) supporting quality assurance (11%), and (c) enabling access control (3%). Finally, formal theory related contributions focus only on issues related to linked data cube integration and exploitation.

If we study the analysis steps according to the types of contribution, we can come up with some interesting results. First, the majority of the publishing contributions are use cases (58%), while software (22%) and vocabularies (18%) follow. The majority of the exploitation contributions are software (57%) with use cases (21%), vocabularies (15%), and formal theories (7%) coming next. Finally, regarding the contributions about combining linked data cubes, 38% are use cases, 29% are software tools, and 25% are theoretical contributions.

We can also combine the “Application Area” dimension with the “Category” dimension. If we do so, we will see that 77% of all software tools are domain independent. The same metric is 82% and 79% in the case of software tools for publishing and exploitation respectively. Interestingly, however, this percentage goes down to 57% in the specific case of software tools that support combining of linked data cubes. On the other hand, 78% of all vocabulary contributions are domain independent. More specifically, domain-specific vocabularies have been developed only for publishing and access control.

We now focus on two specific types of contributions of major importance, namely vocabularies and software. For these two specific categories we present in more detail the contributions so far.

4.1 Vocabularies

Several RDF vocabularies have been proposed to model statistical data as RDF. Two of the first vocabularies introduced were the Statistical Data and Metadata eXchange (SDMX) information model that was proposed to represent statistical data and make them available using web services [21] and the Statistical Core Vocabulary (SCOVO) for modelling and publishing statistical data [49].

Other vocabularies proposed in literature include Open Cubes [34], the vocabulary that models Data Warehouses' cubes [27], the SCOVOLink ontology that extends SCOVO in order to allow the creation of links between the data and the described entities [133] and the LOIUS ontology that also extends SCOVO to describe statistics about University student activities [106]. However the mostly used vocabulary is the RDF Data Cube vocabulary (QB) [23] that models statistical data as RDF. The first version of QB was released on April 2012 but the vocabulary has been a W3C standard since January 2014.

As QB vocabulary became a standard, a number of studies extended it in order to overcome some of the QB's limitations or satisfy specific domains' needs and requirements. For example, the Linked Clinical Data Cube (LCDC) is a vocabulary that combines QB and DDI-RDF in order to allow the publication of clinical data as linked data [75]. Moreover, Bandholtz et al.'s vocabulary is also a SCOVO-based vocabulary that models German Environmental Specimen Bank (ESB), data that describe the accumulation of pollutants/substances in test subjects at specific places over time [9].

Recently, however, the focus has been moved from the definition to the application of vocabularies. For example, Becker et al. [12] performed a quantitative survey on how the QB vocabulary is applied to model multidimensional data. Kalampokis et al. [62] also investigated the challenges related to the different practices that can be followed in applying the QB vocabulary.

Finally, a number of vocabularies facilitate the exploitation of linked data cubes such as the REA (Resources, events, agents) - based model for OLAP cubes [120] and Prat et al.'s model that represents OLAP cubes as an OWL-DL ontology [107, 108]. Another example is the QB4OLAP vocabulary, that extends QB in order to allow implementing OLAP operations on cubes such as rollup, slice, dice and drill-across using SPARQL queries [33, 34, 36]. Finally, Follenfant et al.'s model [38] is an extension to the QB vocabulary that enables the description of analytical processes (e.g. data analysis) that can be performed within reporting tools.

4.2 Software

A number of software solutions have been developed that aim to facilitate the publishing of linked data cubes. For example, the OpenCube toolkit [60, 61, 64] includes a number of open source software components that have been developed to enable data cubes publishing. Specifically, the OpenCube toolkit includes the TARQL extension for the conversion of legacy tabular data to RDF, the D2RQ data cubes extension for the conversion of relational databases to RDF, the JSON-stat2qb data cubes extension for the conversion of JSON-stat files into RDF and the R2RML data cubes extension for data transformation of cubes structured in tabular sources to linked data cubes. Another example is the LOD2 Statistical Workbench [58] that includes a set of tools for accessing, manipulating, exploring and publishing statistical data. Specifically, LOD2 includes tools for importing and editing cubes, and managing their dimensions and code lists.

Moreover, LODStats [32] is a web-based tool that collects and publishes statistics about the LOD cloud. At the same time, OLAP2DataCube [116, 117] and the CSV2DataCube [116] are both plug-ins for the Ontowiki tool for extracting and publishing statistical data in RDF. The two plug-ins enable the publishing of OLAP databases to RDF and CSV data to RDF respectively. Finally, TabLinker [95] is also a tool for publishing excel data as data cubes.

A number of software solutions also enable the exploitation of cubes through browsing. For example, LSD Dimensions [91] is a web-based tool for monitoring dimensions and codes (i.e. variables and values) of data cubes. It provides users with a list of the dimensions of cubes stores in Datahub.io and allows users to browse them. Linked Data Cubes Explorer (LDCX) [69] is another tool that enables the browsing of data cubes. It allows users to select a number of datasets and show and explore their dimensions and measures. The OpenCube Browser [64] is also a tool that provides functionalities for exploring linked open statistical data cubes.

In addition, a number of tools have been developed aiming at producing meaningful charts, maps and other visualisations out of statistical data cubes. Visualisations vary from charts to maps. For example, the OpenCube MapView [64], part of the OpenCube toolkit, enables visualisations of linked data cubes with a geo-spatial dimension on maps. The Interactive chart visualisation widget, also part of the OpenCube toolkit, allows the visualisation of RDF data cubes, in particular, time series data using charts. Another example is the LOD2 Statistical Workbench [57] that provides CubeViz [82, 83], a tool for visualizing a data cube's observations with suitable charts. Moreover, Map4rdf [25] is a browsing tool that allows the exploring and visualisation of RDF data cubes that include geospatial information using maps. Map4rdf supports Google Maps and OpenStreetMap. Map4rdf has also a mobile compatible counterpart, Map4RDiOS app [80] which can be installed in mobile devices with iOS and offers similar functionalities with Map4rdf. Another visualisation tool is the Linked Data Visualisation Model [50] that also includes a plug-in to facilitate the publication of non-data cubes as cubes. The CODE Visualisation Wizard [98, 99, 128] is also a platform that imports statistical data, transforms them to data cubes and suggests and creates visualizations (bar charts, lines, pies etc.) on top of them. Moreover, ETIHQ visual dashboard [115] is a software that allows the visualisation of tourism indicators modelled as data cubes to enhance the decision making of Destination Marketing Organizations. Finally, qb.js [87] is another tool that enables the creation of visualizations from data cubes without requiring knowledge of linked data or semantic tools.

Software related to performing OLAP operations on top of data cubes include the OpenCube OLAP Browser [64], a tool that enables using linked data cubes to perform OLAP operations (such as drill-down, roll-up and pivot) and Saad et al.'s [113] prototype that enables performing OLAP operations on top of data cubes.

Software solutions described in literature also allow performing various types of statistical analysis on top of data cubes. For example, the Linked Open Data

Extension of Rapidminer adds to Rapidminer the Data Cube Importer operator [109]. The operator enables the importing of data model using the QB vocabulary so as to perform a plethora of statistical analyses and predictive analytics functions.

Only a few tools enable the integration of data cubes. The OpenCube Compatibility Explorer of the OpenCube toolkit allows users to identify compatible cubes for potential merge and then establish typed links to facilitate discovery. The OpenCube Expander creates new expanded cubes by merging two compatible cubes. Another example is the LOD2 Statistical Workbench [58] that includes tools for interlinking the dimensions of two data cubes and for enriching data cubes with external data (e.g. data from dbpedia). Bacon [10] is also an open source software that enables the fusion of semantically associated cubes and the integration of related cubes into a single cube. The discovery of relative cubes is based on the structure as well as the content of the cubes. The efficiency of the integration is increased by allowing the modification of the cubes' structure and also by detecting duplicate information in the integrated cube.

Relevant studies propose data quality related tools such as the RDF Data Cube Validation tool, part of the LOD2 Statistical Workbench, that can be used to validate the integrity constraints defined in the QB vocabulary specification and to automatically repair identified errors [56] and Vital [24] that allows the detections of bugs in data cubes (e.g. insufficient documentation, wrong data types, syntax errors in URIs, inconsistencies between data structure specifications and observations). A relevant service for assessing the quality of data cubes is Computex [41] that allows the validation of statistical index data represented as data cubes.

Finally, LiMDAC [65] was introduced as a platform that enables controlling the access to medical data cubes.

5 Conclusions

Statistical data is often organised in a multidimensional manner where a measured fact is described based on a number of dimensions structuring this way a data cube. Linked data technologies have the potential to realize the vision of combining and performing analytics on top of previously isolated cubes across the Web.

In this paper we consolidated the literature in the area of linked data cubes and we analysed and synthesised this body of knowledge in the form of a proposed conceptual framework. This framework was then applied to further analyse the literature and, as a result, we come up with interesting results about this research area. For example, the majority of the contributions that focus on publishing of linked data cubes are use cases while the majority of the exploitation contributions are software tools. Moreover, we identified that the integration of data cubes is still a unexploited research topic.

We should however note that this paper does not present the final results of the analysis of the literature as this is still an ongoing activity.

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